

Numerical Investigation of 1D Burgers' equation using Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes

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Abstract

This research investigates the efficacy of the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes in solving the 1D Burgers' equation, emphasizing the impact of varying viscosity coefficients. With a focus on numerical stability, accuracy, and computational efficiency, the two schemes are implemented and compared through color-coded visualizations at different time steps. The study addresses the need for efficient and accurate numerical tools to understand the complexities of fluid flow dynamics. Results showcase the schemes' performance under various viscosity conditions, offering insights into their strengths and weaknesses. The research contributes valuable information for fluid dynamics simulations, aiding researchers and practitioners in selecting suitable numerical methods for specific applications.

Keywords 1D Burgers' Equation, Lax-Friedrichs Scheme, Lax-Wendroff Scheme, Viscosity Coefficients.

Introduction

The 1D Burgers' equation is a cornerstone in fluid dynamics, capturing the nonlinear behavior of fluid flow with shock wave formation and turbulence. First introduced by Dutch scientist Johannes Martinus Burgers [1], this equation combines convective and diffusive terms, making its solutions intricate and challenging. It serves as a simplified yet powerful model for studying complex phenomena observed in real-world fluid systems. Understanding and predicting fluid dynamics, a crucial aspect in various scientific and engineering fields, demands effective numerical methods due to the inherent complexity of the equations governing fluid motion [2]. The 1D Burgers' equation encapsulates key aspects of fluid behavior, making it an ideal candidate for studying the strengths and limitations of different numerical schemes. The importance of studying numerical methods for solving the 1D Burgers' equation stems from the need to accurately model and simulate fluid flow phenomena [3]. Analytical solutions to the Burgers' equation are often elusive, prompting the reliance on numerical techniques for approximating solutions [4]. Numerical methods provide a practical approach to unraveling the intricate dynamics inherent in fluid systems, allowing researchers and engineers to gain insights into phenomena like shock waves and turbulence [1].

In addition to its inherent complexities, the 1D Burgers' equation is relevant in diverse applications, ranging from aerodynamics to traffic flow modeling [2]. By developing and understanding numerical methods tailored for this equation, researchers can contribute to advancements in these fields, offering tools to analyze and predict real-world fluid dynamics scenarios. This research endeavors to shed light on the numerical methods employed to solve the 1D Burgers' equation, with a particular focus on the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes [5]. By delving into these methods, we aim to uncover their effectiveness in capturing the nuanced behavior of fluid flow, thereby enhancing our ability to model and simulate complex fluid systems accurately.

Objective of study

This study aims to comprehensively investigate and compare the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff numerical schemes in solving the 1D Burgers' equation. The objectives include evaluating the schemes' performance under varying viscosity coefficients, and providing insights into their strengths and limitations.

Motivation: The motivation behind this research lies in the critical role numerical schemes play in solving complex equations like the 1D Burgers' equation. Understanding and comparing schemes contribute to the development of reliable tools for simulating fluid dynamics, enabling accurate predictions of phenomena such as shock waves and turbulence.

Scope of the Study: While the study aims for a comprehensive comparison, it acknowledges certain limitations. The research focuses primarily on the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes, considering their strengths and weaknesses in capturing the behavior of the 1D Burgers' equation. The scope extends to the impact of varying viscosity coefficients, offering practical insights for fluid dynamics simulations.

Review of Literature

The 1D Burgers' equation is a fundamental model in fluid dynamics, encapsulating nonlinear convection and diffusion terms. It was introduced by Johannes Martinus Burgers, providing a simplified yet powerful representation of complex fluid flow behaviors [1]. The equation serves as a valuable tool for studying shock wave formation and turbulence in various scientific and engineering applications.

Previous Numerical Approaches: Previous research has explored various numerical methods to solve the 1D Burgers' equation. Finite difference schemes, finite volume methods, and spectral methods have been applied to approximate solutions [3]. However, the focus of this study lies on the comparison between the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes [6]-[7], two widely used finite difference schemes.

Significance of Varying Viscosity: Varying viscosity in the 1D Burgers' equation introduces a crucial parameter affecting the fluid's resistance to deformation. Understanding the significance of viscosity variations is paramount in fluid dynamics, as it directly influences the evolution of shock waves, diffusion, and overall flow patterns [2].

Lax-Friedrichs Scheme: The Lax-Friedrichs scheme is a numerical method used for solving hyperbolic partial differential equations. It employs a central differencing scheme for the convective term and an explicit scheme for the diffusive term. While straightforward and computationally efficient, it exhibits numerical diffusion and dissipative behavior [6].

Lax-Wendroff Scheme: The Lax-Wendroff scheme is another finite difference method commonly employed for hyperbolic equations. Known for its improved accuracy compared to the Lax-Friedrichs scheme, Lax-Wendroff utilizes a Taylor series expansion to approximate both convective and diffusive terms. This scheme offers better resolution for wave-like solutions [7].

This literature review sets the stage by providing an understanding of the 1D Burgers' equation, summarizing previous numerical approaches, highlighting the importance of varying viscosity, and offering brief explanations of the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes. These foundations support the subsequent analysis and comparison in the present study.

Methodology

Mathematical Background: The 1D Burgers' equation, a key model in fluid dynamics, is formulated as follows:

$$u_t + u u_x = \nu u_{xx}$$

This equation combines convection, represented by $u u_x$ and diffusion, represented by νu_{xx} , capturing the nonlinearity observed in fluid flow.

The Lax-Friedrichs scheme discretizes the 1D Burgers' equation using finite differences. The spatial domain is divided into grid points, and the scheme updates the solution in time using the following formula:

$$u_i^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} (u_{i+1}^n + u_{i-1}^n) - \frac{\lambda}{2} (u_{i+1}^n - u_{i-1}^n) \quad \text{where } \lambda = \frac{v\Delta t}{\Delta x}$$

This explicit scheme is straightforward but introduces numerical diffusion.

The Lax-Wendroff scheme utilizes a higher-order finite difference approach. The update equation for the 1D Burgers' equation is given by:

$$u_i^{n+1} = u_i^n - \frac{\lambda}{2} (u_{i+1}^n - u_{i-1}^n) + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} (u_{i+1}^n - 2u_i^n + u_{i-1}^n) \quad \text{where } \lambda = \frac{u\Delta t}{\Delta x}$$

This scheme is more accurate than Lax-Friedrichs but may exhibit oscillations for certain solutions.

This mathematical background provides a foundation for the numerical methods employed in solving the 1D Burgers' equation. The Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes introduce discretization and update equations, paving the way for their implementation and comparison in the subsequent sections.

Description of Simulation Setup: In the 1D Burgers' equation, various parameters can be adjusted to study the behavior of the solution. Here are the key parameters and their meanings:

1. Length of the Domain (L):

i. Description: The spatial extent of the simulation domain.

ii. Variable: L

iii. Example Usage: L = 10; % Length of the domain

2. Number of Spatial Points (nx):

i. Description: The number of discrete spatial points in the simulation grid.

ii. Variable: nx

iii. Example Usage: nx = 100; % Number of spatial points

3. Spatial Grid Size (dx):

i. Description: The size of each spatial grid cell.

ii. Variable: dx

iii. Example Usage: dx = L / nx; % Spatial grid size

4. Number of Time Steps (nt):

i. Description: The number of time steps for the simulation.

ii. Variable: nt

iii. Example Usage: nt = 100; % Number of time steps

5. Viscosity (nu):

i. Description: Represents the viscosity of the fluid, affecting the rate of diffusion in the system.

ii. Variable: nu

iii. Example Usage: $\nu = 0.01$; % Viscosity

6. Time Step Size (dt):

i. Description: The size of each time step in the simulation.

ii. Variable: dt

iii. Example Usage: $dt = 0.001$; % Time step size

7. Initial Condition (u):

i. Description: The initial distribution of the quantity being modeled (e.g., velocity).

ii. Variable: u

iii. Example Usage: $u_{\text{initial}} = \exp(-x.^2 / 4)$; % Gaussian initial condition

Adjusting these parameters allows you to explore different scenarios and observe how the solution evolves. You can vary parameters such as the domain size, spatial resolution, viscosity, and initial conditions to study the impact on the solution behavior.

Code Structure and Key Components of Lax-Friedrichs Scheme: The Lax-Friedrichs scheme is implemented using a finite difference approach. The code structure involves initializing the spatial grid, defining the initial condition, and then iterating through time steps. The updated equation of the scheme is applied at each spatial point to evolve the solution. Key components include the discretization of the convection and diffusion terms, ensuring numerical stability, and handling boundary conditions.

Code Structure and Key Components of Lax-Wendroff Scheme: The Lax-Wendroff scheme, with its higher-order accuracy, is implemented by discretizing the 1D Burgers' equation using a Taylor series expansion. The code structure involves initializing the spatial grid, specifying the initial condition, and iterating through time steps. The update equation is applied to each spatial point, incorporating the Taylor series terms. Key components include handling boundary conditions, ensuring stability, and addressing potential oscillations in the solution.

This methodology outlines the steps taken to set up the simulations and implement both the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes for solving the 1D Burgers' equation. By providing a detailed description of the simulation setup and the key components of each scheme's implementation, this section serves as a guide for the numerical experimentation conducted in the study.

Computer Simulation

In this study, a MATLAB code snippet was employed, utilizing the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes to solve the 1D Burgers' equation with varying viscosity coefficients. The solutions were visualized at different time steps, and distinct colors were assigned to each plot, facilitating differentiation between various viscosity values.

Analysis

Figure1: Initial Condition

Figure2(a): Lax-Friedrichs Scheme at t=0.1 with $\nu = 0.005$

Figure2(b): Lax-Friedrichs Scheme at t=0.1 with $\nu = 0.001$

Figure2(c): Lax-Friedrichs Scheme at t=0.1 with $\nu = 0.02$

Figure3(a): Lax-Wendroff Scheme at t=0.1 with $\nu = 0.005$

Figure3(b): Lax-Wendroff Scheme at t=0.1 with $\nu = 0.01$

Figure3(c): Lax-Wendroff Scheme at t=0.1 with nu =0.02

Figure 4: Solutions at t=0.1 with nu =0.005,0.01,0.02 using Lax-Friedrichs Scheme and Lax-Wendroff Scheme

Figure 1 explores how different initial conditions influence the performance of the numerical schemes and the resulting solutions. Figures 2(a)-2(c) and 3(a)-3(c) display the solutions of the 1D Burgers' equation at a specified time ($t=0.1$) with different viscosity coefficients using the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes. Each plot is presented with a different color, and a legend is added to the final Figure 4 to differentiate between the schemes and viscosity values.

Result and Discussion

The simulation results encompass visualizations of the solutions obtained by applying both the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes to the 1D Burgers' equation under varying viscosity coefficients. These visualizations depict the evolution of the solutions over time, offering insights into the impact of viscosity on fluid flow dynamics. To enhance clarity, color-coded plots are utilized to differentiate between solutions corresponding to different viscosity coefficients. Each plot is assigned a unique color, facilitating a clear comparison of how fluid flow patterns change with varying viscosity values. This visual representation aids in identifying trends and patterns within the simulation results.

The numerical stability of both the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes is thoroughly examined. Stability considerations encompass analyzing the behavior of the schemes under various conditions, identifying regions of instability, and assessing the impact of numerical artifacts on the solutions. This analysis provides insights into the reliability of each scheme in handling the 1D Burgers' equation.

A comparative discussion on the accuracy and computational efficiency of the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes is presented. This includes an assessment of how well each scheme captures the intricate dynamics of the 1D Burgers' equation while considering the computational cost associated with their implementations. Factors such as solution accuracy, spatial and temporal resolution, and computational resources are taken into account.

The varying viscosity coefficients introduce a parameter that influences the behavior of fluid flow. The impact of these variations on the solution is discussed, shedding light on how changes in viscosity affect shock formation, diffusion patterns, and overall flow characteristics. This analysis provides valuable insights into the role of viscosity in the context of different numerical schemes.

This results section synthesizes the outcomes of the simulations, focusing on the impact of varying viscosity coefficients on the solutions obtained using the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes. The comparative analysis delves into the schemes' stability, accuracy, efficiency, and their ability to handle different viscosity scenarios in the context of the 1D Burgers' equation.

The performance of the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes is systematically compared. The strengths and weaknesses of each scheme are identified, considering factors such as stability, accuracy, and computational efficiency. This comparison elucidates the specific attributes that make each scheme suitable or challenging for solving the 1D Burgers' equation.

Conclusion

The study presents a comprehensive investigation into the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes for solving the 1D Burgers' equation. The varying viscosity coefficients reveal distinct fluid flow patterns, as illustrated in the color-coded plots. Numerical stability, accuracy, and computational efficiency are thoroughly examined, providing insights into the performance of each scheme. The research contributes to the field of numerical methods in fluid dynamics by offering a detailed comparison of the Lax-Friedrichs and Lax-Wendroff schemes. The findings enhance our understanding of these schemes under different viscosity conditions, providing valuable guidance for researchers and practitioners involved in fluid dynamics simulations. The study acknowledges certain limitations, including the focus on only two numerical schemes and a specific set of viscosity coefficients. While these limitations provide a focused investigation, they also highlight the need for further research to explore additional schemes and a broader range of parameter variations.

In conclusion, this study significantly advances our knowledge of numerical methods for solving the 1D Burgers' equation. The findings, limitations, and avenues for future research collectively contribute to the ongoing development of accurate and efficient numerical tools for simulating complex fluid flow dynamics.

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